

BLAST PARAMETER EFFECTS IN FULL SCALE AIR BLAST ON SANDWICH COMPOSITE PANELS

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1 Summary

Blast resistance in composite materials is of increasing importance in naval applications, and this paper presents results of full scale air blast tests of foam composite sandwich panels, as well as developments in modeling of these panels for varying charge sizes and stand-off distances.

2 Introduction

The use of foam sandwich composite materials are of interest in marine applications due to their light weight, high stiffness and energy absorbing properties. They also offer benefits in military applications due to their resistance to radar detection, as they are non-metallic. The recent advancements in polymeric foam sandwich composites has produced cores made of manufactured structural foam such as styrene acrylonitrile (SAN), polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polystyrene sandwiched between GFRP and CFRP skins, some data from which is presented here. The results from the aforementioned tests have been processed to provide graphs showing the effect of scaled distance ($R/W^{1/3}$), where R is stand-off distance and W is TNT equivalent charge size, on panel response. Finite element analysis (FEA) has also been performed with varying stand-off distance for a constant charge size and varying charge size for a constant stand-off distance, to further investigate the effect of each, and this has been compared to experimental results. A pressure - impulse (P-I) failure curve has been produced which shows combinations of peak reflected pressure and reflected impulse on a panel which will cause failure. Finally multiple loading on one panel has been performed with the results presented here, which give an indication of residual strength in the sandwich panel after blast.

3 Materials

The focus of this paper is on one particular configuration of foam sandwich panel which has 2 mm 0°/90°/45° E-glass quadriaxial skins (code:

QE1200) bonded onto a 40 mm thick SAN foam core (code: P800). The material properties of these constitutive parts are provided in Table 1.

4 Air Blast Testing

Full scale air blast tests were performed at RAF Spadeadam, and consisted of 30 kg C4 charges (38.4 kg TNT equivalent) at various stand-off distances. The blast test set up is shown in Fig. 1, where the explosive charge (E) is surrounded by numerous test fixtures (F) containing the composite panels, and a pressure gauge block to measure the blast wave properties. The test fixtures contain two composite panels, as shown in Fig. 2, and inside the test fixtures, located behind each test panel are two high speed cameras to perform digital image correlation (DIC) on the loaded panel. This DIC analysis allowed the response full back face of the panel to be analysed throughout the blast wave loading, to determine if the loading was symmetrical, and if failure happened where this took place and the development of cracks in the panel.

4.1 Progressive Air Blast Loading

In progressively loading the sandwich panels, the stand-off distance was set to 8 m, 12 m, and 16 m with the same charge size, to determine the effect of stand-off on panel response. By measuring the pressure profile from each blast it was possible to plot a pressure versus impulse (P-I) curve for a 30 kg C4 charge showing how pressure and impulse vary with stand-off distance. In order to analytically predict a P-I curve the blast was assumed to be hemispherical (analogous to the explosive being positioned on top of a perfectly elastic foundation) and the targets perfectly perpendicular to the blast wave direction. By assuming a perfectly elastic foundation a correction factor of 2 was applied to the charge size, to account for the hemispherical blast wave [2]. Progressively loading the panel was important as predicting the stand-off of an explosion during a blast is difficult, so numerous values need

to be tested to be able to estimate at what distance the explosive will cause failure of the panel.

4.2 Multiple Air Blast Loading

In order to determine sandwich panel residual strength, a sandwich panel was subject to subsequent blast loading. All blasts used 30 kg C4 explosive, and the stand-off distance was 16 m in the first blast, 14 m in the second, and 8 m in the final blast. This was performed to allow the residual strength on the panels after an initial blast, which did not cause visible cracking in the panel, to be assessed, for assessment of the survivability of a military vessel to multiple attacks. If structural integrity is maintained during a blast, but the material does not remain elastic, this can be utilized to allow design of the structure for a compromise between weight and strength.

5 Finite Element Modeling

Models of the sandwich panels have been produced in order to analyse response and failure of the panel with various charge sizes and stand-off distance applied. The models were created and simulations performed using Abaqus CAE. It is necessary to create full FEA models for loading such as blast on composite panels due to high costs of both blast loading and composite panels. FEA simulations do require validation using test results, and an attempt has been made to do this here by comparison to air blast test data.

5.1 Solid Model of Sandwich Panel

The solid model of the sandwich panel was created using solid C3D8R elements for the foam core, and S4R shell elements for the two skins. For the foam core 3D elements are required to allow through-thickness values to be determined, as crushing of the foam take place as well as movement in the plane of the plate. It was also necessary to attain rate dependent test data for the foam, due to it being highly rate dependent, and this involved testing foam samples in uniaxial compression on a high rate Instron universal testing machine. For the GFRP skins it was acceptable to use 2D elements as it can be assumed that there is no stress in the through-thickness direction due to the very low thickness of the skins compared to the other two dimensions. The meshed model of the sandwich panel is shown in Fig. 3 to give an indication of element size. Only one quarter of the panel was modeled, taking advantage of the symmetry of the panel geometry and the loading. The skins were assumed to be

perfectly elastic, as was the contact between the skin and the core. The panel was assumed to be pinned around the perimeter of the back face and restricted from movement in the plane of the panel around the perimeter of the front face, which are most analogous to actual blast loading conditions without the necessity to create models of the steel frames which clamp the sandwich panel. The only boundary conditions applied to the foam core were in tying it to the skins either side.

5.2 Blast Loading Parameters

Loading was applied via a normal, evenly distributed pressure profile on the front face, the pressure-time trace of which was calculated using the Freidlander equation [2]. Fig. 4 shows the calculated pressure traces which were applied to the finite element models at stand-off distance varying from 8 m to 16 m. The simulations began upon arrival of the blast wave on the panel. The pressure applied to the face was planar, which can be assumed of blast waves which are at a reasonable distance from the sandwich panel. In order to test close proximity blast a significantly different modeling approach would be adopted to allow for the spherical shape of the blast wave interacting with the panel face.

6 Air Blast Results

Presented in this section are the panel deflection results from the air blast tests performed for both progressive and multiple loading. The panel response is measured using DIC on the back face and shown in each case are displacement, principle strain and shear strain.

6.1 Progressive Loading

Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show panel responses for stand-off distances of 8 m, 14 m and 16 m respectively. Also shown in each case is the pressure versus time trace measured by the pressure gauges situated at the same distance from the explosive as the test panel. In Fig. 7 however, the trace is produced analytically using CONWEP, due to data acquisition failing during the blast. The maximum displacement trace in each panel is shown, as calculated using DIC, and in the 8 m and 14 m case this is verified using a laser gauge situated inside the test fixture during the blast. The effect of stand-off distance on displacement is shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen that while the peak pressure in each case drops, the positive pressure duration increases, meaning that it is necessary to calculate the impulse

energy (the area under the positive pressure part of the trace), and how this affects panel response.

6.2 Multiple Loading

The multiple blast load displacements were measured using only a laser gauge at the center and the results of the three stand-off distances is shown in Fig. 9. From the displacements measured it would seem that without the presence of cracking in the panels, the effect on panel strength is negligible.

7 FEA and Blast Test Comparison

In order to determine in more detail the effect of stand-off and charge size on panel response, finite element modeling was performed using Abaqus CAE as described previously. This allows a much less expensive way of assessing panel response and suitability, but must be verified with actual test results. To provide verification of FEA results, simulations were performed at 8 m, 14 m and 16 m stand-off distances with 30 kg C4 charges, to provide direct comparisons with experimental results as will be presented in this section.

7.1 FEA Results at 8 m Stand-Off

The simulation performed at a stand-off distance of 8 m, predicted failure of the front face sheet skin at 1.5 ms. The location of front face failure is shown in Fig. 10, where the principle stress is 258 MPa. At this point the principle strain is 1.5 %, so at the limit of failure according to the material properties stated in Table 1. This skin failure is at the long edge of the plate boundary, the same failure location identified in experimental results, as shown in Fig. 11 where a crack is clearly visible running down the left hand edge of the front face. Core failure has also taken place in this panel, but after the skin had failed. In order to predict core failure in the sandwich panels it would be necessary to incorporate failure data into the FEA, as failure causes dramatic reductions in panel stiffness which then causes further failure due to increased deflection.

7.2 FEA Results at 14 m Stand-Off

A comparison of experimental results and FEA results for the 30 kg C4 charge at 14 m is shown in Fig. 12, showing displacement of the panel, principle strain and shear strain. All measurements are on the back face of the sandwich panel. In the FEA models only one quarter of the panel has been used, with symmetrical boundary conditions around

the edges, and very close correlation with blast test results is shown.

7.2 FEA Results at 16 m Stand-Off

The final stand-off distance tested with 30 kg C4 on 40 mm foam core panels was 16 m. A comparison of results from this test with results from FEA is shown in Fig. 13. It can be seen that the FEA has predicted values of displacement and strain well, but the deflection time is quicker in the FEA than in the actual blast. This is likely due to an extended loading time during the blast as a result of reflection from the ground, an effect which is also seen to a lesser extent in the 14 m stand-off results. However the close agreement in peak values verifies the use of the FEA simulations in predicting damage and the effect on stand-off during blast.

8 Panel Deflection

When failure in the sandwich panel does not occur, it is important to determine the amount of central displacement in the panel, in order to assess the effective stiffness of the sandwich panel, which in turn can be used to make predictions on the response of the overall structure to a blast event. In all panel displacement plots a sinusoidal response is observed, due to displacement in the positive direction from the initial blast pressure, and then a negative 'rebound' due to a reduction in pressure to below ambient in the location of the blast, thus drawing the sandwich panel back out towards the explosion location.

8.1 Effect of Stand-Off on Panel Deflection

As the charge is moved farther away from the target it stands to reason that the pressure and impulse acting on the target decrease. Detonation can take place at any distance from a vessel, so it is important to understand the displacement that will be caused with varying stand-off. Fig. 14 shows the variation in central displacement of the 40 mm thick sandwich panels, when a 30 kg C4 charge is used. These responses were predicted using FEA for cases of 8 m to 16 m stand-off. The displacements at 8 m and 10 m are elastic here, but in reality the panel would have failed at these stand-off distances. However it can be seen that for the 8 m case it is not too different from that observed in the blast test, indicating that panel stiffness is still high after a crack has formed.

8.2 Effect of Charge Size on Panel Displacement

It is also important to understand the effect of different charge sizes being detonated at the same distance from a target, as it is not known what size explosive will be used. Fig. 15 shows the variation in panel displacement with varying charge sizes from 50 kg to 10 kg C4 which were predicted using FEA. In this case the duration of loading does not change as significantly as in the varying stand-off case, due to the impulse being more sensitive to stand-off than charge size.

9 Pressure and Impulse Effects

As shown in Fig. 8, when considering blast loading on structures it is important to consider both the pressure applied, as well as the impulse. In order to predict the effects of changing either charge or stand-off distance it is commonplace to consider the scaled distance, Z , which is the stand-off distance divided by the cubed root TNT equivalent charge size. The variation of peak reflected pressure and impulse with the scaled distance for a 30 kg TNT equivalent charge are shown in Fig. 16, with experimental results from the 8 m and 14m progressive loading cases shown for comparison. However, it is important to consider damage of the panels under all variations of charge and stand-off in order to fully understand the capabilities of the sandwich panel. In order to evaluate this, a failure curve has been produced for varying values of peak pressure and impulse energy, allowing any charge and stand-off to be plotted to find if the panel will fail or survive. Fig. 17 shows the P-I failure curve for the sandwich panels described in Section 3. Table 2 shows the values of reflected pressure and impulse for each stand-off distance for the 30 kg C4 charges, and the damage found from these tests. It is clear to see that these points lie on the correct sides of the P-I curve shown in Fig. 17. The P-I curve was found by varying the charge size and stand-off distances in consecutive simulations using FEA, until damage occurred. Initial failure occurred consistently in the front face in the location shown in Fig. 10.

10 Discussion

Full scale air blast testing has been performed on glass fibre sandwich panels, in order to determine the effect of varying stand-off distance of a 30 kg C4 explosive from the panel. It was found that at 8 m the panel suffered severe skin and core cracking whereas at 14 m and 16 m stand-off distances the panels did not suffer damage. With the use of FEA

the deduction was made that actual panel failure would first begin at around 11 m for a 30 kg C4 charge. FEA was also used to develop a P-I failure curve, which allows any charge size (TNT equivalent) and stand-off distance to be used to assess whether or not the 40 mm thick sandwich panel will fail, and how close to failure it is. The FEA models were successfully verified with the test results at 8 m, 14 m and 16 m, and the effect of maintaining charge size and increasing stand off, and vice versa, were investigated. Finally the effect of applying multiple subsequent blasts to the panel was investigated, and it was found that without skin or core cracks being present the deflection was unchanged, meaning there is negligible residual damage from the previous blast. This is due to the skins being elastic and the first to fail, so without cracking the panel can be assumed to still be elastic. Further investigations will continue into modelling of the blast event, including damage models to assess the response of the panel after cracking has taken place. Also blast testing will continue at different charge sizes and stand-off distances to further verify FEA results.

12 Conclusions

Test results from 30 kg C4 blasts have been presented showing full failure of panels with an 8 m stand-off distance. Also a P-I failure curve has been created to allow the sandwich panels to be assessed for failure for any variation of charge size and stand-off distance.

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Table 1. Material properties of sandwich panel constitutive parts [1].

Material Property	QE1200	P800
Density (kg/m ³)	1750	155
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	17	0.14
Compressive Modulus (GPa)	-	0.13
Tensile Strength (MPa)	260	2.85
Compressive Strength (MPa)	200	2.8
Shear Modulus (MPa)	6500	61
Tensile Failure Strain (%)	1.5	2.2

Table 2. Reflected pressure, reflected impulse and damage measured during 30 kg C4 charges at various stand-off distances.

	Reflected Pressure (kPa)	Reflected Impulse (kPa.ms)	Damage
8m	680	1200	Severe skin and core cracking
14 m	180	490	Non
16 m	112 ¹	449 ¹	Non

¹Predicted Values [2]

Fig. 1. Schematic of air blast set up.

Fig. 2. Front view of test fixture.

Fig. 3. Meshed model of the sandwich panel for FEA.

Fig. 4. Calculated pressure traces for 30 kg C4 at various stand-off distances.

Fig. 5. Air blast results for 30 kg C4 charge at 8 m stand-off.

Fig. 7. Air blast results for 30 kg C4 charge at 16 m stand-off.

Fig. 6. Air blast results for 30 kg C4 charge at 14 m stand-off.

Fig. 8. Maximum displacement time traces for the three different tests, the first at 16 m stand-off, the second at 14 m stand-off and the third at 8 m stand-off.

Fig. 9. Central displacement of a single test panel blasted consecutively at 16 m, 12 m and 8 m stand-off distances.

Fig. 10. Front face failure location at 1.5 ms in the 30 kg C4 blast simulation at 8 m stand-off.

Fig. 11. Damage in the core and front face of the panel with a 30 kg C4 charge at 8 m stand-off.

Fig. 12. Experimental and FEA results for a 30 kg C4 charge at 14 m stand-off.

Fig. 13. Experimental and FEA results for a 30 kg C4 charge at 16 m stand-off.

Fig. 14. Variation of central panel displacement with stand-off distance.

Fig. 15. Variation of central panel displacement with charge size.

Fig. 16. Pressure and impulse values versus scaled distance for a 30 kg C4 charge size [2]. Also shown are values measured in the 8m and 14m stand-off progressive loading cases.

Fig. 17. PI curve for various charges and stand-off distances found using FEA. Also shown are values measured in the 8 m and 14 m stand-off progressive loading cases, with descriptions of damage found.